

A Study on Job Satisfaction Among Workers in Private Banks with Special Reference to Salem District

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: September

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Jaganath, C. "A Study on Job Satisfaction Among Workers in Private Banks With Special Reference to Salem District."

Shanlax International Journal of Commerce, vol. 7, no. S1, 2019, pp. 17–22.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3412457>

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Abstract

Job satisfaction would result in utmost outcome of the human resources that increases the effectiveness and efficiency of the workers, and thereby resulting in great evolution in any sector. The bank employees might face dissatisfaction in the job due to certain elements like banking structures, advancements, job environment, etc. This study aims at identifying the determinants that are accountable for satisfaction or dissatisfaction of the employees working in private sector banks in Salem district. And it also aims at finding a solution to make the employees comfortable and satisfied with the job, and to remove the dissatisfaction factors to give better productivity. 50 respondents have been taken as sample for the study. The study declared that the option of Salary would be the first motivational factor for their job satisfaction, with 47%, followed by rewards and recognitions with 31%.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, Factors determining job satisfaction, Importance of Job Satisfaction, Banking industry.

Introduction

Banking industry in India is mounting in a much rapid rate in the recent years. It is considered to be the vital industry without which the day-to-day life is impossible in many fields. Since, in the modern years everything has become digitalized and most of the transactions are undertaken digitally, banks are vibrant to be considered. Bank jobs attracts many people and hence job satisfaction of the workers in such banks plays a predominant role for the growth and revolution in banking sector. Emergence of new developments, modifications, revolutions have become challenging for the employees in banking industry now a days, which have a direct effect on their job satisfaction. Only if the workers work with satisfaction, they could be effective in the tasks they do and this would help in the progress, productivity and profitability of banks. A proficient bank will ponder and take into account the importance of such employees' job satisfaction to make a good progress in their banks.

Review of Literature

Dr. Mayuri Chaturvedi, Sumedha Raavi (2019) conducted a research article titled, “A Study on Employee Job Satisfaction in Different Sectors”. In their study employee job satisfaction belonging to four different sectors have been considered which are Education Sector, Public Sector, Private Sector and IT Sector. The research study exposed that though job satisfaction in each field is not considered separately, it provides the overall rate of job satisfaction, the reasons for job satisfaction and also the level of satisfaction with various factors of employees belonging to various sectors.

Mohammad Abdolshah, Seyed Amir Mohammad Khatibi and Mostafa Moghimi (2018) conducted a study on, “Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction of Banking Sector Employees”. The aim of the paper is to focus on the relative importance of factors of job satisfaction and their influence on the employees’ overall job satisfaction. It concluded that the factors such as colleagues, upgrade, and compensation variables are respectively in the first, second, and third place influencing job satisfaction.

Afshan Ali, Irfan Hussain Khan, M Akram Ch, Asmara Sehar Akram Ch, (2018) done a study on “Level of Job Satisfaction among Employees of Banking Industries at Lahore 2016”. The study examined the individual and organizational factors of job satisfaction. It discovered the relationship between job satisfaction and its factors and also considered which factor has the strongest effect on job satisfaction of employees’. The research showed that individual factors like gender, age, personality, marital status and organizational factors like recognition & rewards, pay, promotion prospects, relationship with supervisor & co-workers, fringe benefits, working conditions, work itself and tenure had a significant positive relationship with job satisfaction, except qualification of employees which had insignificant relationship with it. It also showed that the strongest impact on the level of job satisfaction was the pay and the weakest impact was the relationship with co-workers.

Md. Siddikur Rahman, Md Nazmul Haq, Mohammad Maksudul Karim (2017), “An Analysis on Job Satisfaction of Employees in Govt. Banks: A Study on Janata Bank Limited”. The study analysed level of satisfaction among Govt. bank employees. It revealed the findings that good loan facilities but average level of allowance and other incentives for the employees, moderate pleasing leave facilities, good chance for the worker training, reasonable promotion system, etc. It also showed that dissatisfactory aspects with respect to allowance, promotion system, and other incentives, should be removed.

Definition of Job Satisfaction

Keith Davis said that “Job satisfaction is a set of the favourable or unfavourable feelings with which employees view their work.”

According to Vroom, “Job satisfaction is generally considered to be an individual’s perceptual or emotional reaction to important parts of work.”

The Eminence of Job Satisfaction on Bank Employees

Job satisfaction is related to many important aspects, some of which are employee absenteeism, worker performance, turnover, etc.

- Absenteeism of employee: When an employee is not satisfied with the job he does, then it is quiet natural that absenteeism of that particular employee would be more. Hence job satisfaction has a direct impact on absenteeism of employees. An employee will like to attend the work depending upon his satisfaction level in the job. If he is satisfied with the job, he would like to work even if he is really unwell. But at the same time, if he is dissatisfied, he would deliberately avoid going for work even if he is well enough.

- Performance of employee: Of course, the employee performance is determined by the job satisfaction. A satisfied employee is able to give his maximum productivity when compared to an employee who is not satisfied with his job. As L.M.Saari & T.A.Judge (2004)⁶ said, the connection between job satisfaction and job performance is higher for difficult jobs than for less difficult jobs. Hence, the job must be in a pleasing and satisfying way for the employees to bring the best performance and output from them.
- Loyalty of the employee: The loyalty, reliability and trustworthiness of the employees also depends upon the satisfaction level of the employees. It is obvious that an employee would be loyal and faithful to the organization, if they are satisfied with the parameters in the job, and it would definitely be vice-versa if it is the other way. Hence, an organization to earn a loyal employee, should satisfy him.
- Retention of employee: Retention of an employee in any field is a challenge task. The banks should take proper measures to retain its workers. The job in which the employee is involved should be satisfying to him, else he'll go in search for some other job. Hence, a gratified worker prefers to retain in the same job, whereas a worker who is not pleased will definitely hunt for some other job. Hence, job satisfaction is associated with retention of employees.

Means in Which Job Satisfaction of Bank Employees Can Be Amplified

For the purpose of giving maximum progress, the banking industry should concentrate more on what can be done and in what ways the employees can be made satisfied with their job. Some of the methods and ways that the employees can be made satisfied are:

- Pay/Salary: If the banks wish to give more productivity, then it must also be ready to give a reasonable salary or pay for the employees according to their job category and pressure in work. Offering competitive pay will satisfy the employees to work even harder.
- Rewards / Recognitions: Positive feedbacks and providing rewards and thereby recognizing the employees for the work carried out well will satisfy them, and it will automatically result in motivation of the employee to give more progress than before.
- Proper training: Before giving any new tasks, the banks should provide the employees, a proper training about the work they are going to do. This would help them feel confident and satisfied to carry out the new tasks without any hesitation or fear.
- Social Association: When the employees are stimulated to grow social association with others, it would satisfy them and the aspect of teamwork will also be developed. Social association with the co-workers is very vital in banking sector, since it will result in greater efficiency and success of the organization, making the workers also to be satisfied.
- Policy and Plan of the bank: When the bank's policies and plan are unbiased and translucent to all the employees, it leads to more satisfaction on part of the employees. The workers will not have the thought that they are degraded and treated partially than others, when the plans and policies are applied equally to all.
- Job Safety: The banks should guarantee the safety and security of the employees' job, mainly at the period of economic ambiguity. Giving assurance of his job, will increase the job satisfaction of the employee.
- Working Atmosphere: The working atmosphere plays a predominant role in satisfaction of the workers. When the working environment factors like, space area, lighting, ventilation, water and bathroom facilities, etc. are taken proper care by the organisation, it will make the employee enthusiastic, and will have a positive effect in job satisfaction.
- Sense of responsibility: The employees should feel that they are the owner of their work. They should be given such freedom, which will make them feel satisfied and that they are responsible for their work. And thereby they tend to work with utmost care to give more output.

- Some of the other important factors that determines Job Satisfaction are:
- Every employee should have the freedom of speech. He should feel free in communicating his ideas and thoughts in the workplace.
- The employees should feel comfy in expressing his views to his higher officials like manager, supervisor, etc.
- Conducting promotional activities for the employees can be undertaken by the banks. So that they feel they have scope for their improvement, resulting in job satisfaction.
- A noble assistance, support and respect that the employees get from their management will make them feel privileged and satisfied.
- Making the employees comfortable by guiding them in balancing both their work and family would also please them.
- The employees should be provided with necessary equipment to undertake the job in a better manner, which would satisfy them.
- Progression in the career of employees will have a firm job satisfaction.
- The bank's operation, hygiene and motivational factors are imperative for the employees' job satisfaction.

Objectives

1. To evaluate the factors that are responsible for job satisfaction of the employees working in private banks in Salem district.
2. To suggest measures to deprive the negative or dissatisfaction aspects in the job, and also to recommend the ways in which the employees' job satisfaction can be improved.

Research Methodology

Primary data has been gathered with the help of questionnaire. Data has been collected from the employees who are working in 4 different private sector banks in Salem district, Tamil Nadu (Lakshmi Vilas Bank, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank, and Tamilnad Mercantile Bank). The secondary data for the study have been collected with the help of Books, Journals, and Websites. The sampling method that has been used for the study is Random sampling and a sample of 50 respondents were taken for the study. Utmost care have been taken in filling the questionnaires and it was completed appropriately without any bias. All the 50 questionnaires have been distributed among the employees and were filled in. Hence, the response rate is 100 percentage.

Major Findings From the Study

The major findings that has been derived from the study conducted are listed below:

- **Demographic Variables:** Most of the respondents are male with 60%, whereas remaining 40 percent are female. And almost, i.e. 84 percent of the respondents are married. A maximum of 31% are between the age group of 25-35 years of age.
- **Satisfaction Level in the Job:** Majority of the employees are satisfied with their job. The response rate indicated that almost 48% of the workers are satisfied.
- **Working Atmosphere:** A maximum of 61% of the employees are satisfied with the atmosphere in which they are working, which makes the employees feel better.
- **Recognitions and Rewards:** When it comes to recognising the employees and rewarding them for their good work, only 28 percentage of the workers are satisfied with that factor. And only 4% are highly satisfied.
- **Remuneration / Salary:** 49 percentage of the employees are satisfied and none are highly satisfied with the remuneration or salary provided to them.

- Opportunity for Career Development: 48 percentage of the respondents agree that they find opportunities for the growth and development of their career.
- Most Satisfying Factor: Most of the respondents chose the option of Salary as the first motivational factor for their job satisfaction, with 47%, followed by rewards and recognitions with 31%.
- Workload Factor: A maximum of 53% of the employees are satisfied with the workload provided to them. This means that those 53% are provided with fair workload.

Suggestions

- Only 49 percent are satisfied with the remuneration they are provided by the bank. This may be due to growth in the monetary rate of economy, they find their salary insufficient.
- The bank should take more care in considering the recognition and rewards provided. The employees must be provided increments, incentives, allowances, etc. in a satisfying way for them.
- The bank should provide opportunity for proving the talent of every employee impartially. So that they feel inspired and satisfied, and would give their best progress in the job.
- The work given to the employees should not be more that they find it difficult and unsatisfied to complete. A fair workload will make them feel good.
- 61% of the employees are satisfied with the working condition in the bank. None are highly satisfied. The management should take this into account, why the remaining are not satisfied and find what's the problem and try to sort it out. So that all the employees will be satisfied with the atmosphere of work.

If all these suggestions are considered and fixed by the bank management, then there would be more chances for the banks to give better productivity than they are giving at present. And there by, the progression of banks will inevitably be ensured.

Conclusion

The common factors that influence the satisfaction level in the job were taken for the study. And the remuneration factor is considered to be not much satisfied by most of them. The motivational factors like rewards and recognition were also not up to the satisfaction level of employees. These are most important for the employees to feel satisfied with their job. Guidance regarding how to carry out the work in an easy and effective way should be provided to each employee. This will make them carry out their job with satisfaction and confidence. Workload factor should be taken utmost care since it would lead the employee to stress resulting in job dissatisfaction.

References

1. Dr. Mayuri Chaturvedi, Sumedha Raavi, "A Study on Employee Job Satisfaction in Different Sectors". International Journal of Scientific Engineering and Research (IJSER), Volume 7, Issue 1, January 2019, ISSN (Online): 2347-3878, Impact Factor (2018): 5.426,
2. Mohammad Abdolshah, Seyed Amir Mohammad Khatibi and Mostafa Moghimi, "Factors Influencing Job Satisfaction of Banking Sector Employees (The case study: Asgariyeh and MehrIran Banks in Qazvin and Alborz, Iran)". Journal of Central Banking Theory and Practice, 2018, 1, pp. 207-222. DOI: 10.2478/jcbtp-2018-0009.pp.105-108.
3. Afshan Ali, Irfan Hussain Khan, M Akram Ch, Asmara Sehar Akram Ch, "Level of Job Satisfaction among Employees of Banking Industries at Lahore 2016". European Online Journal of Natural and Social Sciences 2018; Vol. 7, No.3(s) Special Issue on Contemporary Research in Social Sciences, pp. 92-108, ISSN: 1805-3602.

4. Md. Siddikur Rahman, Md Nazmul Haq, Mohammad Maksudul Karim, “An Analysis on Job Satisfaction of Employees in Govt. Banks: A Study on Janata Bank Limited”. IOSR Journal of Business and Management (IOSR-JBM), e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668. Volume 19, Issue 6. Ver. III (June 2017), PP 18-25.
5. bconsi.blogspot.com
6. Lise M. Saari and Timothy A. Judge, “Employee attitudes and job satisfaction”. Volume-43, Issue-4, Special Issue: The Contributions of Psychological Research to Human Resource Management, winter 2004, Pages 395-407.